
CAPITAL INTENSITY AND TAX AVOIDANCE: EVIDENCE FROM MULTINATIONAL MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study is to ascertain the effect of capital intensity on tax avoidance of Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. The study specifically ascertains the effect of fixed asset intensity on effective tax rate and the book-tax differences of Multinational Manufacturing Companies. The study adopted the ex post facto research design. The final sample comprised of ten (10) multinational manufacturing Companies based on data availability during the study period, 2012-2024. The data were analyzed using the Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares (EGLS) technique. The results revealed that fixed asset intensity has a positive and significant effect on effective tax rate and on book-tax differences. In conclusion, the study submits that capital intensity has a significant effect on tax avoidance of listed multinational manufacturing firms in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. The study recommended that the Chief Financial Officers (CFOs) and Finance Directors of Multinational Manufacturing Firms should incorporate comprehensive tax planning into capital budgeting decisions in order to ensure that investments in fixed assets are evaluated not only for operational efficiency but also for their long-term tax implications; Board Audit Committees of Multinational Manufacturing Companies should regularly assess how capital investment strategies affect both accounting income and taxable income, and implement governance measures that ensure alignment with fair reporting and tax transparency standards.

Key words: Capital intensity, tax avoidance, fixed asset intensity, effective tax rate, book-tax differences, multinational, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing companies are one of the important sectors in the Nigerian economy. They are the key drivers for economic growth. As companies operating in this sector, they often face strategic decisions regarding capital, capital structure and asset management (Fitriani, & Nindah, 2022). On the other hand, manufacturing companies must also fulfill tax obligations in accordance with applicable laws and regulations (Fitriani, & Nindah, 2022). Tax is one of the main sources of state revenue that plays an important role in supporting national development (Makkatul & Lucky, 2024). It is a mechanism for collecting state revenues and an instrument of a country's fiscal policy (Corinna & Dwi, 2022). However, tax is a burden for the company (Rinaldi, 2020; Alsaadi, 2020). Taxes are viewed as a burden that can reduce a company's net profit and are contrary to the company's goal of maximizing profits (Wardana & Wulandari, 2021). Company management is interested in maximizing profits by streamlining various burdens, including avoiding tax (Corinna & Dwi, 2022). Business entities seek to reduce tax payments by avoiding tax (Kurniasih, Sari, & Maria, 2013). Tax avoidance is a legal method used to minimize the amount of income tax owed by an individual or a business (Devi & Muhyarsyah, 2021). Tax avoidance means paying as little tax as possible while still staying on the right side of the law (Vivek, 2025). Tax avoidance is taking action to minimize tax obligations within the legal framework, while tax evasion is taking illegal actions to avoid paying taxes (Aumeerun, Jugurnath, & Soondrum, 2016). The main goal of practicing tax avoidance is to minimize one's tax liability (Driya and Ety, 2023).

Capital intensity is a factor that is indicated to influence tax avoidance action (Christin & Naniek, 2021). Capital intensity, or the extent to which a company relies on assets and capital investments in its operations, can have a significant impact on tax avoidance practices (Winarta, Siburian, Simorangkir, & Sitepu, 2024). Capital intensity shows how much a company invests in its assets in the form of fixed assets, inventory and stock assets (Gina, Mia, Fithri, Iwan, & Izzul, 2024; Ketut, Thom, & Harry, 2023; Bianca & Einde, 2024). According to Gina, Mia, Fithri, Iwan, and Izzul (2024) capital intensity is used to carry out tax avoidance, especially through Investment in fixed assets. Fixed assets are assets that have a useful life of more than one year and experience depreciation over the useful life of the fixed assets (Amalia, 2019; Putra, Yuliusman, & Wisra, 2020). Companies emphasize capital intensity or tend to choose to invest more in fixed assets, because fixed assets incur depreciation expense (Melliza & Kusumawati, 2023; Siboro & Santoso, 2021). This depreciation expense is a cost that can be deducted from income in the calculation of corporate tax; hence, the more fixed assets a business owns, the higher the depreciation, which lowers the taxable income and effective tax rate (Indira & Chalarce, 2025). The greater the depreciation expense borne, the lower the tax rate that must be paid by the company (Melliza & Kusumawati, 2023). Therefore, a higher proportion of fixed assets is linked to a lower effective tax rate for the company (ETR) (Driya & Ety, 2023).

Most prior studies on capital intensity and tax avoidance were foreign studies and also from the reviewed literatures, (and to the best of our knowledge), the effect of capital intensity on tax avoidance using the fixed asset intensity has not been sufficiently examined in Nigerian manufacturing sector. So, there is need for further research on the fixed asset intensity to examine its connection with the tax avoidance of Multinational manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Again the fiscal year of this study was extended to 2024 contrary to prior studies in Nigeria whose financial period ended in 2023. This created a gap in literature which this study filled. The study is therefore set out to tackle the issues raised above in order

to ascertain the effect of capital intensity on tax avoidance of Listed Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to ascertain the effect of capital intensity on tax avoidance of Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. The Specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Ascertain the effect of fixed asset intensity on effective tax rate of Listed Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.
2. Examine the effect fixed asset intensity on book-tax differences of Listed Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Capital Intensity

Capital intensity is also referred to as fixed asset planning. Capital intensity is how much a company invests in its assets in the form of fixed assets, inventory and stock assets (Keristiani, Rina, & Prihatin, 2024). Capital intensity is an investment made in the form of fixed assets in order to increase profits made by managers of a company (Astri, Nera, & Cahyadi, 2023). Capital intensity is a form of financial decision to invest in fixed assets that incur depreciation costs (Siboro & Santoso, 2021). According to Christin and Naniek (2021), the greater the depreciation expense, the smaller the tax burden that must be paid by the company (Christin & Naniek, 2021). As depreciation costs for an asset increases, the tax paid by the company decreases (Yana, Muhamad, Agus, Radhi & Emil, 2024). Investment in fixed assets provides an opportunity for companies to minimize their tax burden (Sugeng & Zaman, 2020). For the purpose of this study, fixed asset intensity is used as a measure of capital intensity.

2.1.2 Tax Avoidance

There is no universally accepted definition of corporate tax avoidance in the literature (Annuar, Salihu, & Obid, 2014; Hanlon & Heitzman, 2010). Terms such as “Tax Planning”, “Aggressive Tax Planning” and “Abusive Tax Planning” are common in the literature. According to Andre and Murtanto (2024) another term that is often used to express tax avoidance is aggressive tax planning. Tax avoidance is an effort to reduce or even eliminate tax obligations without violating applicable tax regulations (Puspitasari, Anggraeni, & Pasaribu, 2018). According to Drake, Lusch, and Stekelberg (2019) Tax avoidance is a legal effort made by companies to reduce tax obligations by exploiting loopholes in tax regulations. Tax avoidance actions are carried out with the aim of reducing, avoiding, minimizing or lightening the tax burden (Marlinda, Titisari & Masitoh, 2020). For the purpose of this study, effective tax rate (ETR) and book-tax differences (BTD) are used as measures of tax avoidance.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Agency Theory. The separation between owners and managers creates an agency relationship (Olotu, Salawu, Adegbe, & Akinwunmi, 2019). According to Jensen and Meckling (1976) an “agency relationship refers to a “contract under which one or more persons (the principal(s) engage another person (the agent) to perform some service on their behalf which involves delegating some decision-making authority to the agent”.

Agency theory explains how the behavior of related parties in companies that have different interests can cause conflicts of interest (Sahara, 2022). The government or tax authorities see tax as one of the main sources of revenue that plays an important role in supporting national development, while Companies see tax payment as a burden or expense that can reduce the company's net income (Makkatul & Lucky, 2024; Alsaadi, 2020; Wardana & Wulandari, 2021). This situation creates a conflict of interest between the tax authorities and companies (Mukhtaruddin, Jerikho, & Umi, 2024). Companies, acting as agents, aim to reduce tax payments, while tax authorities, acting as the principal, seek the highest possible tax revenue from taxpayers (Olivia & Dwimulyani, 2019).

2. 3 Empirical Review

Gina, Mia, Fithri, Iwan, and Izzul (2024) examined the effect of fixed asset intensity and company size on tax avoidance of Islamic commercial banks. The study obtained data from secondary data derived from the financial statements of the corporate entities studied through Idx.com, kemenkeu.co.id and also from financial statement documents that have been published by each Islamic Commercial Bank registered with the OJK for the period 2018-2022. The population of the study was 35 Islamic Commercial Banks registered with the Financial Services Authority during the 2018-2022 period. Purposive sampling technique was used to determine a sample size of 7 Islamic Commercial Banks. The method used in this study is the panel data regression analysis method with the Common Effect model. The results of the study indicate that partially (t-test) fixed asset intensity does not affect tax avoidance, while company size has a significant positive effect on tax avoidance. And the results of the study indicate that simultaneously (f-test) fixed asset intensity and company size do not affect tax avoidance.

Khairunissa, ferry and Dianwicakasih (2024) examined the Influence of capital intensity, advertising intensity and transfer pricing on tax aggressiveness. Data collected for this study was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regression. The sample size comprises of 95 companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2019-2022. Purposive sampling technique was used to determine the sample size. This study utilized secondary data obtained from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) and related company websites. The results revealed that capital intensity variable has no influence on tax aggressiveness, while the advertising intensity variable has an influence on tax aggressiveness, and the transfer pricing variable has an influence on tax aggressiveness. The study recommended among others that the Government should formulate more effective policies to increase tax compliance and state revenues Mayang and Christina (2023) examined the effect of capital intensity, transfer pricing, and sales growth on tax avoidance with company size as a moderation variable. The study was based on a sample of 124 manufacturing companies in the consumer goods industry listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2018-2021 period. The sampling method used was purposive sampling. The study adopted panel data regression analysis for the analysis. The results revealed that capital intensity and sales growth have a positive effect on tax avoidance, while transfer pricing has no effect on tax avoidance. Firm size is able to weaken the effect of capital intensity and sales growth on tax avoidance. Firm size is unable to moderate the effect of transfer pricing on tax avoidance.

Andrea and Donny (2023) examined the impact of leverage, capital intensity, inventory intensity, cash effective tax rate on tax avoidance: assessment for energy sector corporate. The study adopted the following testing statistical procedures: the classical assumption test, panel data regression analysis, coefficient of determination test, and partial test. The study was undertaken on the energy sector businesses listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange

(IDX) during the period spanning from 2016 to 2019. A purposive sampling strategy was employed to choose 22 companies, comprising a dataset of 88 observations. The data were subjected to analysis and hypothesis testing using the STATA software. A panel data estimation model determination test was conducted, which indicated that the standard effect model was appropriate for this research. The study revealed a notable favorable impact of leverage and inventory intensity on CETR. In contrast, the effect of capital intensity on CETR was shown to be statistically insignificant.

Ketut, Thom, and Harry (2023) examined the effect of earning management and fixed asset intensity on tax management with management compensation as intervening variable in Indonesia. The data source used in this study is secondary data in the form of published company financial reports. The population of the study consisted of 76 primary consumer goods manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the 2017-2021 period. Purposive sampling technique was used to determine a sample of 64 companies or 120 research sample data. The analytical method used in this study is the panel data linear regression method. The results show that partially earnings management has a significant effect on tax management, but asset intensity still has no effect on management tax. And simultaneously earnings management and fixed asset intensity affect tax management. Management compensation can mediate the effect of earnings management on tax management, but management compensation cannot mediate the effect of fixed asset intensity on tax management.

3. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The ex post facto research design was adopted in this study. Secondary data, precisely annual reports and accounts of Multinational manufacturing companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group for the period 2012–2024 were solely deployed. Information from the financial statements were obtained in respect of the following variables: Fixed asset intensity; Effective tax rate (ETR); Book-tax differences; Leverage (LEV), Firm size (FS); Firm age (FA). The population of this study consists of eleven (11) listed Multinational manufacturing Companies on the Nigeria Exchange (NGX) Group as at the end of 2024 financial year. Ten (10) Multinational manufacturing companies were sampled using purposive sampling technique, based on availability of data needed for the study. The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to analyse the data. Descriptive statistic comprises measures such as the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values, Skewness, Kurtosis statistics. The hypotheses were tested using panel estimated generalised least squares. It was used to predict the value of a variable based on the value of the other variables. Multiple regression was used to validate the hypotheses.

3.1 Model Specification

$$ETR_{(i,t)} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 CI_{(i,t)} + \beta_2 Leverage_{(i,t)} + \beta_3 FS_{(i,t)} + \beta_4 FA_{(i,t)} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$BTD_{(i,t)} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 CI_{(i,t)} + \beta_2 Leverage_{(i,t)} + \beta_3 FS_{(i,t)} + \beta_4 FA_{(i,t)} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

$ETR_{(i,t)}$ = Effective Tax Rate of firm i at time t

$CI_{(i,t)}$ = Capital Intensity (Ratio of total fixed assets to total assets) of firm i at time t

$BTD_{(i,t)}$ = Book-tax differences of firm i at time t

α_0 = Constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients of the regression

$Leverage_{(i,t)}$ = Leverage of firm i at time t

$FS_{(i,t)}$ = Firm Size of firm i at time t

$FA_{(i,t)}$ = Firm Age of firm i at time t
 μ = Error term

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Test of Hypotheses

4.1.1 Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Fixed asset intensity has no significant effect on effective tax rate of Listed Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

Table 1: Panel estimated generalised least squares testing the effect of CI on ETR

Dependent Variable: ETR

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)

Date: 06/25/25 Time: 16:18

Sample: 2012 2024

Periods included: 13

Cross-sections included: 10

Total panel (balanced) observations: 130

Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CI	0.005417	0.000489	11.06805	0.0000
LEV	-0.007459	0.000567	-13.14709	0.0000
FS	-0.153994	0.012636	-12.18666	0.0000
AGE	-0.002876	0.000537	-5.359836	0.0000
C	1.260523	0.080125	15.73192	0.0000
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.801320	Mean dependent var		0.924251
Adjusted R-squared	0.794962	S.D. dependent var		4.530202
S.E. of regression	1.004308	Sum squared resid		126.0793
F-statistic	126.0380	Durbin-Watson stat		1.835458
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Eviews 10 Output (2025)

Table 1 presents the test of Hypothesis I, which examines the effect of capital intensity (CI) on effective tax rate (ETR). The model is statistically valid, with a probability of F-statistic = 0.0000, indicating that the model as a whole is significant at the 5% level. The adjusted R-squared of 0.7949 shows that nearly 79.5% of the variation in ETR is explained by the model. The Durbin-Watson statistic (1.84) suggests the residuals are uncorrelated, enhancing model reliability. The intercept (1.2605, $p = 0.0000$) indicates that if all independent variables are held constant, the baseline effective tax rate is 126.05%.

The coefficient of Capital Intensity (CI) is 0.0054 ($p = 0.0000$), meaning that a one-unit increase in CI leads to a 0.54% increase in ETR, holding other variables constant. This positive and significant effect suggests that capital-intensive firms tend to pay more in taxes, possibly due to lower access to aggressive tax shelters or because fixed assets are taxed less flexibly.

4.1.2 Hypothesis Two

Ho2: Fixed asset intensity has no significant effect on book-tax differences of Listed Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

Table 2 Panel estimated generalised least squares testing the effect of CI on BTD

Dependent Variable: BTD

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)

Date: 06/25/25 Time: 16:19

Sample: 2012 2024

Periods included: 13

Cross-sections included: 10

Total panel (balanced) observations: 130

Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CI	0.000977	7.75E-05	12.60438	0.0000
LEV	0.002576	4.60E-05	55.94066	0.0000
FS	0.015127	0.003256	4.646030	0.0000
AGE	-0.001173	0.000190	-6.187887	0.0000
C	-0.069314	0.019728	-3.513404	0.0006

Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.965776	Mean dependent var	-0.879868
Adjusted R-squared	0.964681	S.D. dependent var	8.195031
S.E. of regression	1.016735	Sum squared resid	129.2188
F-statistic	881.8565	Durbin-Watson stat	1.875091
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Eviews 10 Output (2025)

In Table 2, the model tests the effect of fixed asset intensity (CI) on book-tax differences (BTD). The F-statistic probability is 0.0000, validating the model, while the adjusted R-squared is 0.9647, indicating that over 96% of BTD variation is explained by the model—another highly robust regression. The Durbin-Watson stat of 1.88 indicates a lack of significant autocorrelation. The constant is also significant and negative ($\beta = -0.0693$, $p = 0.0006$), implying a small baseline book-tax shortfall.

The coefficient for Capital Intensity (CI) is 0.0010 ($p = 0.0000$), indicating that a one-unit increase in CI leads to a 0.1% increase in BTD, all else equal. Though small, this effect is statistically significant and suggests that capital-intensive firms have a slightly wider gap between book and taxable income, possibly leveraging depreciation allowances and capital tax incentives. Leverage and firm size again show positive effects, while firm age negatively affects BTD.

4.1.5 Discussion of Findings

The finding that capital intensity has a positive and significant effect on effective tax rate ($\beta = 0.0054$, $p = 0.0000$) indicates that firms with a higher proportion of fixed assets relative to total assets tend to bear a higher tax burden. This outcome may be due to the nature of fixed assets in Nigeria, which often come with fewer immediate tax benefits, especially if

depreciation methods are not fully tax-deductible or are heavily regulated. Unlike in developed economies where capital investments are incentivized with tax reliefs, Nigerian tax policy may not offer sufficient allowances for capital expenditures, thereby causing capital-intensive firms to face relatively higher effective tax rates.

Lastly, the result that capital intensity has a positive and significant effect on book-tax differences ($\beta = 0.0010$, $p = 0.0000$) implies that as firms invest more in fixed assets, the discrepancy between accounting and taxable income increases. This can be attributed to the differences in depreciation methods and timing between accounting and tax reporting systems. For instance, while accounting standards may require straight-line depreciation, tax regulations might permit accelerated depreciation. This leads to temporary differences in income recognition, which manifest as book-tax differences. Thus, capital-intensive firms naturally report higher BTDs due to timing mismatches and the complex tax treatment of fixed assets.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study assessed the effect capital intensity on tax avoidance of Listed Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. The study obtained data from annual reports, account and publications from the Nigerian Exchange Group for the Multinational manufacturing Companies that operated during 2012-2024. In addition, the correlation of specific capital intensity such as fixed asset intensity and dependent variable measures such as effective tax rate and book-tax differences were assessed. To determine the relationship that exists amongst the variables and the effect thereof, Pearson correlation coefficient and panel estimated generalised least squares were employed. This study revealed that fixed asset intensity has a positive and significant effect on effective tax rate and on book-tax differences. In conclusion, the study submits that capital intensity has a significant effect on tax avoidance of Listed Multinational Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria at 5% level of significance.

Based on the study findings, the following were recommended:

The Chief Financial Officers (CFOs) and Finance Directors of Multinational Manufacturing Firms should incorporate comprehensive tax planning into capital budgeting decisions in order to ensure that investments in fixed assets are evaluated not only for operational efficiency but also for their long-term tax implications.

Finally, board Audit Committees of Multinational Manufacturing Companies should regularly assess how capital investment strategies affect both accounting income and taxable income, and implement governance measures that ensure alignment with fair reporting and tax transparency standards.

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